

Summer Games Report - Kurunji

Model Predictive Control for Lidar-Assisted Wind Turbine Pitch Control

IEA Wind Task 52 – LAC Summer Games 2025

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Abstract

This report presents the design and implementation of a Model Predictive Controller (MPC) for Lidar-assisted collective pitch control of the IEA 15 MW reference wind turbine. The MPC replaces the conventional 1D feedforward lookup table in the ROSCO controller architecture, using linearized OpenFAST models and Lidar wind preview as a measured disturbance. A custom unconstrained QP solver based on pre-computed prediction matrices achieves an 18.41 % reduction in the competition cost function compared to the ROSCO+LAC baseline for the 4BeamPulsed Lidar configuration on the 30s sprint (DLC 1.4). The report details the system architecture, MPC formulation, state estimation approach, and the challenges encountered when integrating predictive feedforward control alongside an existing PI feedback controller.

1 Introduction

Wind turbines operating in the above-rated wind speed regime rely on collective pitch control to regulate rotor speed and limit structural loads. Conventional closed-loop pitch controllers such as the proportional-integral (PI) regulators used in ROSCO [3] can only react to wind disturbances after they reach the rotor, inherently limiting the achievable load reduction. The performance ceiling of purely reactive control is set by the bandwidth of the pitch actuator and the closed-loop dynamics: by the time a sudden gust is detected at the rotor, the mechanical system has already begun to accelerate.

Lidar-Assisted Control (LAC) overcomes this limitation by exploiting advance wind measurements from a nacelle-mounted Light Detection and Ranging (Lidar) sensor. A pulsed Lidar emits laser pulses and analyses the Doppler frequency shift of the backscattered signal from aerosol particles naturally present in the air, yielding line-of-sight (LOS) wind velocity components at discrete range gates several rotor diameters upstream. Under the *Taylor frozen turbulence* hypothesis which assumes the wind field is advected past the turbine by the mean wind speed \bar{v} with negligible evolution a measurement at upstream distance d provides information about the wind state that will arrive at the rotor after a preview time. For a 4-beam pulsed Lidar with a usable focal distance on the order of $d \approx 100\text{--}200$ m upstream of the rotor and above-rated wind speeds of 12–20 m/s, this preview time is typically in the range of about 5–17s, sufficient to preemptively adjust the blade pitch angle before an approaching gust reaches the rotor. The LOS measurements from multiple beams are geometrically reconstructed into a scalar Rotor Effective Wind Speed (REWS) estimate that represents the spatially averaged wind speed across the rotor disc. A buffer accumulates the filtered REWS history, producing both the current wind estimate REWS_b (delayed to align with the

rotor) and a forward-looking REWS preview vector spanning the full preview horizon.

Figure 1 illustrates the LAC control architecture. The Lidar preview signal feeds a feedforward controller whose pitch command is superimposed on the existing PI feedback signal, forming a two-degree-of-freedom control structure: the feedback loop provides robust closed-loop stability and rejects unmeasured disturbances, while the feedforward path uses the wind preview to reduce the residual excitation that the feedback loop would otherwise need to correct [1].

Figure 1: Lidar-Assisted Control (LAC) concept.[1]

LidarAssistedControl Summergames 2025: The IEA Wind Task 52 LAC Summer Games 2025 challenges participants to optimize this feedforward strategy for the IEA 15 MW reference wind turbine under extreme coherent gust conditions (DLC 1.4). The competition cost function to minimize is:

$$J = \frac{\max |\Omega - \Omega_0|}{\Omega_0} + \frac{\max |M_T - M_{T,0}|}{M_{T,0}} \quad (1)$$

where $\Omega_0 = 7.56$ rpm and $M_{T,0} = 158.3 \times 10^3$ kN-m are the steady-state rotor speed and tower base fore-aft moment, respectively.

The baseline approach uses ROSCO’s PI feedback loop for rotor speed regulation combined with a 1D lookup table for Lidar-assisted feedforward pitch control. The lookup table maps the current REWS estimate to a steady-state pitch angle; its time derivative provides a feedforward pitch rate to the feedback controller. While effective, this approach discards the temporal structure of the wind preview: only the instantaneous REWS value is used, ignoring the fact that the full preview vector reveals the wind trajectory over the next several seconds.

This work replaces the 1D lookup table with a Model Predictive Controller that exploits the full Lidar wind preview horizon. Rather than reacting only to the current wind estimate, the MPC uses the predicted future wind trajectory to compute an optimal pitch sequence that minimizes rotor speed deviation and tower base moment over a receding prediction horizon, as illustrated in fig. 1.

2 System Architecture

2.1 Integration with ROSCO

The MPC operates within the existing ROSCO Simulink architecture as a feedforward controller. It replaces the `gain_scheduled` lookup table block while preserving the downstream signal path:

1. The MPC S-Function receives four inputs: current wind speed ($REWS_b$), generator speed Ω , the 551-element wind preview vector ($REWS_preview$), and the actual blade pitch angle from OpenFAST.
2. The MPC computes an optimal pitch angle θ_{MPC} [rad].
3. A discrete derivative block ($\Delta u/\Delta t$) converts the pitch angle to a pitch rate.
4. The pitch rate is multiplied by a gain and added to ROSCO's feedback pitch rate.
5. The combined pitch rate passes through the pitch actuator model before reaching the turbine.

Figure 2: MPC integration within the ROSCO Simulink architecture. The MPC replaces the gain-scheduled lookup table as a feedforward controller, while the existing PI feedback loop remains active for closed-loop stability.

This architecture ensures that ROSCO's PI feedback loop remains active for closed-loop stability, while the MPC provides anticipatory feedforward action based on the Lidar preview.

3 MPC Formulation

3.1 Linearized Plant Model

The MPC uses linearized models obtained from OpenFAST at operating points spanning 12.0 to 19.5 m/s in 0.5 m/s increments (15 operating points). Each linearization yields a continuous-time state-space model:

$$\dot{x} = Ax + B_w v + B_u \theta, \quad y = Cx + D_w v + D_u \theta \quad (2)$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^6$ contains the full plant states, v is the wind speed deviation from the operating point, θ is the collective pitch deviation, and y contains the outputs of interest.

3.1.1 State Vector

The OpenFAST linearization provides 6 states which are retained in full. All six states are used directly in the MPC prediction and Kalman observer, as collective pitch has meaningful coupling to tower fore-aft dynamics through the rotor thrust.

Table 1: Full state vector from OpenFAST linearization (6 states).

Index	State	Unit	Description
1	q_{FA}	m	1st tower fore-aft displacement
2	q_{SS}	m	1st tower side-to-side displacement
3	ψ	rad	Generator azimuth angle
4	\dot{q}_{FA}	m/s	Tower fore-aft velocity
5	\dot{q}_{SS}	m/s	Tower side-to-side velocity
6	Ω	rad/s	Rotor speed

The row order above reflects the six degrees of freedom retained in the linearization (two tower modes, generator azimuth, and their velocities); the precise index assignment follows the ordering written by OpenFAST into the .lin file and is consumed as-is by the design script, so the MPC and observer are indifferent to the specific permutation.

3.1.2 Output Vector

Two outputs are used in the prediction cost:

- **Rotor speed** Ω [rpm]: Output index 9 in the OpenFAST linearization. Because rotor speed is itself a state (index 6 in table 1), the corresponding row of the C matrix picks out that state and scales it by $30/\pi \approx 9.5493$ to convert rad/s to rpm:

$$C_{[\Omega]} = [0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 30/\pi] \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 6}.$$

- **Tower base fore-aft moment** M_T [kN-m]: Output index 12. Unlike the rotor speed row, this output depends on several states through the tower dynamics; its row in C is dense and is read directly from the .lin file.

For the MPC prediction cost, Ω and M_T are used. For the Kalman observer, Ω and blade pitch angle θ are used as measurements, since blade pitch is directly available from OpenFAST while tower base moment is not.

3.2 Discretization and Prediction Matrices

The continuous model is discretized at $T_s = 0.1$ s (10 Hz) using zero-order hold. A second discretization of the same model at $T_{s,o} = 0.01$ s is used for the Kalman observer (section 4). The MPC-rate system reads:

$$x_{k+1} = A_d x_k + B_{d,w} v_k + B_{d,u} \theta_k, \quad y_k = C_d x_k + D_{d,w} v_k + D_{d,u} \theta_k \quad (3)$$

For a prediction horizon of P steps and control horizon of C steps, the predicted output over the horizon is:

$$\mathbf{y} = \Psi x_0 + \Theta_u \mathbf{U} + \Theta_w \mathbf{W} \quad (4)$$

where:

- $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{R}^{P \cdot n_y}$: stacked predicted outputs over the horizon
- $\Psi \in \mathbb{R}^{P n_y \times n_x}$: free response matrix, $\Psi_k = C_d A_d^k$
- $\Theta_u \in \mathbb{R}^{P n_y \times C}$: control response matrix (with hold for $k > C$)
- $\Theta_w \in \mathbb{R}^{P n_y \times P}$: disturbance response matrix (lower-triangular)
- $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^C$: pitch deviation trajectory
- $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^P$: wind deviation trajectory from preview

3.3 Cost Function and QP Formulation

The MPC minimizes a quadratic cost:

$$J_{\text{MPC}} = \mathbf{y}^T Q \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{U}^T R_u \mathbf{U} + \Delta \mathbf{U}^T R_{\Delta u} \Delta \mathbf{U} \quad (5)$$

where Q is a block-diagonal output weighting matrix assembled separately for each operating point:

$$Q_i = I_P \otimes \begin{bmatrix} Q_\Omega & 0 \\ 0 & Q_M / \sigma_i^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

with Q_Ω penalizing rotor speed deviation and Q_M penalizing tower moment deviation. The scaling factor

$$\sigma_i = \frac{\bar{M}_{T,i}}{\bar{\Omega}_i} \quad (7)$$

is built from the operating-point tower moment and rotor speed at the i -th linearization, keeping the relative weight between the two output channels roughly constant across the gain schedule.

R_u penalizes the absolute pitch deviation, and $R_{\Delta u}$ penalizes the pitch rate through the differencing matrix D_Δ :

$$R_{\Delta u} = D_\Delta^T \bar{R}_{\Delta u} D_\Delta, \quad D_\Delta = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & & & \\ -1 & 1 & & \\ & \ddots & \ddots & \\ & & & \ddots \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Substituting eq. (4) into eq. (5) and taking the gradient yields the unconstrained optimum:

$$\mathbf{U}^* = -H^{-1} (F_w \mathbf{W} + F_x x_0) \quad (9)$$

where:

$$H = \Theta_u^T Q \Theta_u + R_u + R_{\Delta u} \quad (10)$$

$$F_w = \Theta_u^T Q \Theta_w \quad (C \times P) \quad (11)$$

$$F_x = \Theta_u^T Q \Psi \quad (C \times n_x) \quad (12)$$

The matrices H^{-1} , F_w , and F_x are pre-computed in Script 1 (algorithm 1) for each operating point. At runtime, the MPC solve reduces to a single matrix-vector multiplication.

3.4 Pitch Constraints

Physical constraints are enforced as post-optimization saturation on the output of the unconstrained QP solve. The S-Function applies them in the following three-step sequence to prevent rate-limit windup:

1. **Angle clamp:** θ_{raw} is clamped to $[-5^\circ, 90^\circ]$, yielding θ_{clamped} .
2. **Rate clamp:** the increment $\delta = \theta_{\text{clamped}} - \theta_{\text{prev}}$ is limited to $|\delta| \leq 8^\circ/\text{s} \cdot T_s = 0.8^\circ$, giving $\theta_{\text{cmd}} = \theta_{\text{prev}} + \delta$.
3. **Re-clamp:** θ_{cmd} is clamped once more to $[-5^\circ, 90^\circ]$ to guard against any residual violation from the rate step.

Because the limits are applied after the QP solve rather than embedded as inequality constraints, the optimizer is unaware of the saturation. This is computationally efficient but means the internal model sees a different input sequence than the one actually sent to the actuator whenever a limit is active.

4 State Estimation

4.1 Discrete Kalman Filter

The MPC requires a state estimate \hat{x} at each solve step. A discrete Kalman filter provides this estimate by running a predict–correct cycle at the full Simulink base rate of 100 Hz, one order of magnitude faster than the 10 Hz MPC solve. This two-rate scheme ensures the state estimate remains current between QP solves.

4.1.1 Observer System

A separate LTI observer system is discretized at $T_{s,o} = 0.01$ s from the same OpenFAST linearization:

$$x_{k+1} = A_o x_k + B_{o,w} v_k + B_{o,u} \theta_k \quad (13)$$

$$y_k = C_o x_k + D_{o,w} v_k + D_{o,u} \theta_k \quad (14)$$

where the observer output vector contains two measurements:

$$y_k = \begin{bmatrix} \Omega_{\text{meas}} - \bar{\Omega}_{i^*} \\ \theta_{\text{meas,deg}} - \bar{\theta}_{\text{deg},i^*} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^2 \quad (15)$$

Rotor speed (rpm deviation) and blade pitch angle (degree deviation) are both available as real-time measurements from OpenFAST. A minor unit-convention note: $B_{o,u}$ is expressed in radians (from the OpenFAST linearization) while the pitch output row of C_o is in degrees (OpenFAST reports `BldPitch1` in degrees). The two quantities are never added directly, so no unit conflict arises.

4.1.2 Kalman Gain Design

The steady-state Kalman gain is pre-computed for each operating point by solving the Discrete Algebraic Riccati Equation (DARE):

$$P = A_o P A_o^T - A_o P C_o^T (C_o P C_o^T + R_{\text{kf}})^{-1} C_o P A_o^T + Q_{\text{kf}} \quad (16)$$

$$L = P C_o^T (C_o P C_o^T + R_{\text{kf}})^{-1} \quad (17)$$

with process noise $Q_{\text{kf}} = \text{diag}(10^{-4}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-4}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-3})$ and measurement noise $R_{\text{kf}} = \text{diag}(0.01, 0.001)$.

4.1.3 Predict–Correct Cycle (100 Hz)

At every 0.01 s Simulink step the observer performs a two-step update using the previous step’s wind speed and pitch command as known inputs:

$$\hat{x}^- = A_o \hat{x} + B_{o,w} v_{k-1} + B_{o,u} \theta_{k-1} \quad (18)$$

$$\hat{y}^- = C_o \hat{x}^- + D_{o,w} v_{k-1} + D_{o,u} \theta_{k-1} \quad (19)$$

$$\hat{x} = \hat{x}^- + L (y_k - \hat{y}^-) \quad (20)$$

The corrected estimate \hat{x} is then available as x_0 for the MPC QP solve whenever the decimation counter triggers (every 10 steps). The prediction step propagates the model with the previous commanded pitch θ_{prev} , while the correction step uses the measured blade pitch from port 4. This is standard Kalman structure – commanded input drives the model, measured output drives the correction – but worth stating explicitly since both signals are called “pitch” in the code.

5 Gain Scheduling

The wind turbine is a nonlinear system, and the linearized models are only valid near their operating points. A gain-scheduling strategy switches between 15 MPC controllers (one per operating point from 12.0 to 19.5 m/s in 0.5 m/s steps) based on the current wind speed REWS_b.

The nearest-neighbor scheduling selects the operating point closest to the current wind:

$$i^* = \arg \min_i |v - v_i| \quad (21)$$

The corresponding pre-computed matrices (H^{-1} , F_w , F_x) and Kalman observer matrices (A_o , $B_{o,w}$, $B_{o,u}$, C_o , L) are used for the QP solve and state observer respectively. The pitch output is referenced to the selected operating point:

$$\theta_{\text{cmd}} = U^*(1) + \bar{\theta}_{i^*} \quad (22)$$

6 Implementation

The implementation divides cleanly into two scripts. In the first script, a MATLAB script reads all 15 OpenFAST linearization files, builds the MPC prediction and gain matrices for each operating point, and saves the results to a `.mat` file. In the second script, a Level-2 MATLAB S-Function loads this file once at initialization and then applies the pre-computed matrices in real time. Because the unconstrained QP solution (eq. (9)) reduces to a single matrix–vector product, the computational cost per control step is negligible, enabling a 10 Hz effective solve rate within the 100 Hz Simulink loop.

6.1 Script 1: Gain Matrix Pre-computation

For each operating point $v_i \in \mathcal{V}$, the design script performs the following steps: it reads the OpenFAST `.lin` file, extracts the full 6-state model, discretizes two separate systems – an MPC prediction system at $T_s = 0.1$ s and a Kalman observer system at $T_{s,o} = 0.01$ s – both using zero-order hold, builds the Toeplitz-structured prediction matrices Ψ , Θ_u , Θ_w via the Markov parameter recursion, assembles the block-diagonal cost matrices, inverts H to obtain the closed-form MPC gain matrices, and solves the DARE to obtain the steady-state Kalman gain L . All results are serialized to `MPC_Custom_All.mat` and loaded by the S-Function at the first Simulink time step. The complete procedure is given in algorithm 1 (Appendix A).

6.2 Script 2: S-Function Runtime

The S-Function runs at the Simulink base rate of 100 Hz. At *every* step the Kalman observer (eqs. (18) to (20)) is updated using the current Ω , blade pitch measurement, and the previous step’s wind and pitch command. An internal counter decimates the QP solve to 10 Hz (every $d_{\text{dec}} = 10$ steps). Between QP solve steps the previous pitch command is held, so the actuator sees a staircase signal at 10 Hz while the state estimate continues to evolve at 100 Hz.

On the very first Simulink call the persistent data structure is empty: the S-Function loads `MPC_Custom_All.mat`, sets an initial pitch of $\theta_{\text{prev}} = 0.1276$ rad ($\approx 7.31^\circ$, the steady-state pitch for the 12.5 m/s operating point), and seeds the observer’s previous-input memory with $v_{\text{last}} = 12.5$ m/s and $\theta_{\text{last}} = 0.1276$ rad so that the first predict step uses a self-consistent operating-point state.

Gain scheduling selects the nearest operating point by minimizing $|v - v_i|$ at every solve step. The REWS preview vector (551 elements at 100 Hz) is downsampled by a factor of $d_s = 16$ with a fixed one-sample lead offset before being passed to the QP solve. The complete runtime logic is given in algorithm 2 (Appendix A).

7 Results

7.1 30 s Sprint – 4BeamPulsed Configuration

The MPC controller was evaluated against the feedback-only baseline and the ROSCO+LAC (feedback + feedforward with 1D lookup table) on the DLC 1.4 extreme coherent gust scenario.

Table 2: Competition cost function results (4BeamPulsed, DLC 1.4).

Controller	Cost (J)
Baseline (FB only)	2.851024
ROSCO + LAC (FBFF)	0.722838
MPC (Kurunji)	0.589773
Improvement vs. ROSCO+LAC	18.41 %

The MPC achieves an 18.41% reduction in the total cost function relative to the ROSCO+LAC baseline. The improvement reflects the controller’s ability to exploit the full temporal structure of the Lidar wind preview: rather than mapping the instantaneous REWS to a steady-state pitch angle, the MPC computes a pitch trajectory that accounts for the wind speed evolution over the entire 1.2 s prediction horizon, allowing earlier and more precisely timed pitch adjustments ahead of the arriving gust.

7.2 Cost Decomposition

To identify which load channel drives the improvement, table 3 breaks the scalar cost J into its two constituent terms (eq. (1)), reporting the peak deviations in engineering units alongside their normalized contributions.

Table 3: Peak deviations and cost-term decomposition (4BeamPulsed, DLC 1.4). $J_\Omega = \max |\Omega - \Omega_0|/\Omega_0$ and $J_M = \max |M_T - M_{T,0}|/M_{T,0}$, with $\Omega_0 = 7.56$ rpm and $M_{T,0} = 158.3 \times 10^3$ kN-m.

Controller	$\max \Delta\Omega $ [rpm]	J_Ω [-]	$\max \Delta M_T $ [kN-m]	J_M [-]	J [-]
Baseline (FB only)	1.8098	0.2394	413 422	2.6116	2.8510
ROSCO + LAC (FBFF)	0.3001	0.0397	108 141	0.6831	0.7228
MPC (Kurunji)	0.1820	0.0241	89 550	0.5657	0.5898
Relative reduction vs. ROSCO+LAC	—	39.3 %	—	17.2 %	18.4 %

Two observations follow from the decomposition. First, in *relative* terms the largest improvement is on rotor speed regulation: the peak RPM excursion drops from 3.97% of Ω_0 for ROSCO+LAC to 2.41% for the MPC, a 39.3% reduction. This is the direct benefit of solving over a horizon rather than mapping a single instantaneous REWS value to a steady-state pitch angle – the MPC can begin pitching earlier and ramp the command along a trajectory that matches the gust profile. Second, in *absolute* contribution to the competition cost the tower-moment term dominates: of the $\Delta J = 0.133$ reduction achieved by the MPC, $\Delta J_M = 0.1174$ comes from the tower-moment channel and only $\Delta J_\Omega = 0.0156$ from the rotor-speed channel, i.e. roughly 88% of the cost improvement is tower-load reduction. This is a direct consequence of including M_T as a second output in the prediction model and placing significant weight on it via Q_M .

Figure 3 shows the time-domain response of all three controllers across the sprint window.

8 Challenges and Lessons Learned

8.1 ROSCO Interaction and State Estimation

A significant challenge was the interaction between the MPC feedforward and ROSCO’s PI feedback. Since the MPC’s internal model does not include ROSCO’s feedback actions, a naive observer accumulating errors from the MPC-commanded inputs alone diverged from reality. The resolution was to design the Kalman observer using the actual inputs seen by the plant (wind measurement and actual blade pitch from OpenFAST) rather than the inputs assumed by the MPC. This decouples the observer from the MPC’s internal model and allows the state estimate to remain consistent with the true closed-loop behaviour.

8.2 Hyperparameter Tuning: Horizons and Weights

The final values $P = 12$, $C = 1$, $Q_\Omega = 5$, $Q_M = 10^6$, $R_u = 0.01$, and $\bar{R}_{\Delta u} = 10^5$ were obtained from a sweep over each parameter. The sweep procedure was: hold all other hyperparameters fixed, vary the parameter of interest, and recompute J on the DLC 1.4 sprint until a minimum was found.

Longer prediction horizons ($P > 20$) caused the MPC to over-anticipate the gust, pitching aggressively several seconds before the disturbance arrived. With $C > 1$ the optimizer traded near-term performance for long-term optimality, producing a non-minimum-phase-like initial response. Shorter horizons ($P < 8$) discarded a meaningful portion of the preview. The $P = 12$ choice corresponds to a 1.2s lookahead at $T_s = 0.1$ s.

The control horizon was fixed at $C = 1$ after all $C > 1$ cases under-performed. With the MPC solving around a zero-initial-state assumption every decimation step, multi-step plans were being optimized for a fictional future state that would never actually be re-used (only the first move is applied before

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Figure 3: DLC 1.4 30s sprint results: wind speed, collective pitch angle, rotor speed Ω , and tower base fore-aft moment for the feedback-only baseline (blue), ROSCO+LAC feedforward (orange), and Kurunji MPC (green dash-dot). Cost annotations at the bottom correspond to the competition cost function J .

the next solve). The rate-penalty coupling between planned moves then biased the first-move decision. Collapsing to $C = 1$ removed this coupling entirely.

The output weights $Q_\Omega = 5$ and $Q_M = 10^6$ were tuned jointly after the per-operating-point scaling σ_i was in place. Increasing Q_M produced monotone improvement in tower load up to $Q_M = 10^6$, beyond which rotor-speed tracking began to degrade. The rate penalty $\bar{R}_{\Delta u} = 10^5$ was set to the smallest value that suppressed high-frequency pitch chatter.

8.3 Pitch Rate and Tower Excitation

The MPC output passes through a derivative block before entering ROSCO. Aggressive pitch changes translated to large pitch rate spikes, exciting the tower's first fore-aft mode. Adding M_T as a second output in the prediction cost, combined with strong rate penalties ($\bar{R}_{\Delta u} = 10^5$), mitigated this issue.

9 Conclusion

A gain-scheduled linear MPC was successfully implemented for Lidar-assisted collective pitch control of the IEA 15 MW turbine, achieving an 18.41 % reduction in the competition cost function compared to the ROSCO+LAC baseline. The key design choices were:

- Custom QP solver using pre-computed prediction matrices (single matrix multiply at runtime)
- Discrete Kalman filter running at 100 Hz with Ω and blade pitch measurements, decoupled from the MPC's internal model to avoid fighting ROSCO
- $C = 1$ control horizon to prevent non-minimum-phase trajectory optimization
- Multi-objective cost function balancing Ω and M_T
- Post-optimization pitch rate and angle constraints

A Code Listings

Algorithm 1: MPC Design via Linear Parameter Varying Linearisation

```

Input: Wind grid  $\mathcal{V} = \{12.0, 12.5, \dots, 19.5\}$  m/s;;
 $T_s = 0.1$  s;;
 $T_{s,o} = 0.01$  s;;
 $P = 12$ ;;
 $C = 1$ ;;
 $Q_{\text{kf}}$ ;;
 $R_{\text{kf}}$ 
Output: MPC_Custom_All.mat – pre-computed gain and observer matrices for all operating points
foreach operating point  $v_i \in \mathcal{V}$  do
  Step 1: Read Linearisation;
  Load  $(A, B, C, D, u_{\text{op}}, y_{\text{op}})$  from .lin file at  $v_i$ ;
  Step 2: Trim & Extract Operating Point;
  Select inputs: wind disturbance (col. 1), pitch (col. 9);
  MPC outputs:  $\Omega$  (row 9),  $M_T$  (row 12);
  Observer outputs:  $\Omega$  (row 9),  $\theta_{\text{deg}}$  (row 5);
  Store  $\bar{v}_i, \bar{\theta}_i, \bar{\Omega}_i, \bar{M}_{T,i}, \bar{\theta}_{\text{deg},i}$ ;
  Step 3a: Discretise MPC System at  $T_s = 0.1$  s;
  Form MPC system:  $(A, B_{[w,u]}, C_{[\Omega, M_T]}, D_{[\Omega, M_T]})$ ;
   $A_d, B_{d,w}, B_{d,u}, C_d, D_{d,w}, D_{d,u} \leftarrow \text{c2d}(\cdot, T_s)$ ;
  Step 3b: Discretise Observer System at  $T_{s,o} = 0.01$  s;
  Form observer system:  $(A, B_{[w,u]}, C_{[\Omega, \theta_{\text{deg}}]}, D_{[\Omega, \theta_{\text{deg}}]})$ ;
   $A_o, B_{o,w}, B_{o,u}, C_o, D_{o,w}, D_{o,u} \leftarrow \text{c2d}(\cdot, T_{s,o})$ ;
  Step 4: Build MPC Prediction Matrices;
  Initialise  $\Psi \in \mathbb{R}^{Pn_y \times n_x}$ ,  $\Theta_u \in \mathbb{R}^{Pn_y \times C}$ ,  $\Theta_w \in \mathbb{R}^{Pn_y \times P}$ ;
  for  $k \leftarrow 1$  to  $P$  do
     $\Psi_{[k]} \leftarrow C_d A_d^k$ ; // free-response row
    for  $j \leftarrow 1$  to  $C$  do
      if  $k = j$  then
         $\Theta_{u,[k,j]} \leftarrow D_{d,u}$ ;
      else if  $k > j$  then
         $\Theta_{u,[k,j]} \leftarrow C_d A_d^{k-j-1} B_{d,u}$ ;
      end
    end
    Apply move-blocking: replicate column  $C$  for  $j > C$ ;
    for  $j \leftarrow 1$  to  $k$  do
      if  $k = j$  then
         $\Theta_{w,[k,j]} \leftarrow D_{d,w}$ ;
      else
         $\Theta_{w,[k,j]} \leftarrow C_d A_d^{k-j-1} B_{d,w}$ ;
      end
    end
  end
  Step 5: Assemble MPC Cost Matrices;
   $\sigma_i \leftarrow \bar{M}_{T,i} / \bar{\Omega}_i$ ; // normalisation ratio
   $Q_{\text{blk}} \leftarrow \text{diag}(Q_\Omega, Q_M / \sigma_i^2)$ ;  $Q \leftarrow I_P \otimes Q_{\text{blk}}$ ;
   $R \leftarrow R_u + D_\Delta^\top \bar{R}_{\Delta u} D_\Delta$ ;
  Step 6a: Compute and Invert Hessian;
   $H \leftarrow \Theta_u^\top Q \Theta_u + R$ ;
   $F_w \leftarrow \Theta_u^\top Q \Theta_w$ ;  $F_x \leftarrow \Theta_u^\top Q \Psi$ ;
  Step 6b: Compute Steady-State Kalman Gain (DARE);
   $P \leftarrow \text{dare}(A_o^\top, C_o^\top, Q_{\text{kf}}, R_{\text{kf}})$ ;
   $L \leftarrow P C_o^\top (C_o P C_o^\top + R_{\text{kf}})^{-1}$ ;
  Step 7: Store;
  Save  $H^{-1}, F_w, F_x, P, C$  to mpc_data{i}; 13
  Save  $A_o, B_{o,w}, B_{o,u}, C_o, D_{o,w}, D_{o,u}, L$  to mpc_data{i};
  Save  $\bar{v}_i, \bar{\theta}_i, \bar{\Omega}_i, \bar{M}_{T,i}, \bar{\theta}_{\text{deg},i}$  to op_array(i);
end
Serialise mpc_data and op_array to MPC_Custom_All.mat;

```

Algorithm 2: MPC S-Function Execution Logic (Script 2, per Simulink step at 100 Hz)

Input: v [m/s];
 Ω [rad/s];
 $v_{\text{preview}} \in \mathbb{R}^{551}$;;
 θ_{actual} [rad]
Output: θ_{cmd} [rad]
Initialisation (first call only);
 Load MPC_Custom_All.mat into persistent MPC_DATA;
 Set $\theta_{\text{prev}} \leftarrow 0.1276$ rad; step counter $\leftarrow 0$;
 $\hat{x} \leftarrow \mathbf{0}_{6 \times 1}$; $v_{\text{last}} \leftarrow 12.5$ m/s; $\theta_{\text{last}} \leftarrow 0.1276$ rad;
 Output $\theta_{\text{cmd}} \leftarrow 0.1276$ rad; **return**;
Increment step counter;
Read v , Ω , v_{preview} , θ_{actual} from input ports;
Gain scheduling (every step);
 $i^* \leftarrow \arg \min_i |v - \bar{v}_i|$; // nearest operating point
Retrieve A_o , $B_{o,w}$, $B_{o,u}$, C_o , $D_{o,w}$, $D_{o,u}$, L and \bar{v}_{i^*} , $\bar{\theta}_{i^*}$, $\bar{\Omega}_{i^*}$, $\bar{\theta}_{\text{deg},i^*}$;
Kalman observer predict-correct (every step at 100 Hz);
 $\Delta v_{\text{last}} \leftarrow v_{\text{last}} - \bar{v}_{i^*}$; $\Delta \theta_{\text{last}} \leftarrow \theta_{\text{last}} - \bar{\theta}_{i^*}$;
 $\hat{x}^- \leftarrow A_o \hat{x} + B_{o,w} \Delta v_{\text{last}} + B_{o,u} \Delta \theta_{\text{last}}$; // predict
 $\hat{y}^- \leftarrow C_o \hat{x}^- + D_{o,w} \Delta v_{\text{last}} + D_{o,u} \Delta \theta_{\text{last}}$;
 $y_{\text{meas}} \leftarrow \begin{bmatrix} \Omega \cdot \frac{30}{\pi} - \bar{\Omega}_{i^*} \\ \theta_{\text{actual}} \cdot \frac{180}{\pi} - \bar{\theta}_{\text{deg},i^*} \end{bmatrix}$; // rpm dev, pitch-deg dev
 $\hat{x} \leftarrow \hat{x}^- + L(y_{\text{meas}} - \hat{y}^-)$; // correct
 $v_{\text{last}} \leftarrow v$; $\theta_{\text{last}} \leftarrow \theta_{\text{prev}}$;
if not a decimation step ($\text{mod}(\text{step}, d_{\text{dec}}) \neq 1$) **then**
 | output $\theta_{\text{cmd}} \leftarrow \theta_{\text{prev}}$; **return**;
end
MPC QP solve (every 10th step at 10 Hz);
Retrieve $H_{i^*}^{-1}$, F_{w,i^*} , F_{x,i^*} ;
Preview downsampling;;
 $w \leftarrow v_{\text{preview}}(1 + \text{lead} : d_s : \text{end})$; $W \leftarrow w_{1:P} - \bar{v}_{i^*}$; // wind deviation over horizon
Unconstrained QP solve;;
 $U^* \leftarrow -H_{i^*}^{-1}(F_{w,i^*} W + F_{x,i^*} \hat{x})$;
 $\theta_{\text{raw}} \leftarrow U_1^* + \bar{\theta}_{i^*}$; // absolute pitch
Post-optimization constraint enforcement;;
 $\theta_{\text{clamped}} \leftarrow \text{clamp}(\theta_{\text{raw}}, -5^\circ, 90^\circ)$;
 $\delta \leftarrow \text{clamp}(\theta_{\text{clamped}} - \theta_{\text{prev}}, -\Delta\theta_{\text{max}}, +\Delta\theta_{\text{max}})$;
 $\theta_{\text{cmd}} \leftarrow \text{clamp}(\theta_{\text{prev}} + \delta, -5^\circ, 90^\circ)$;
 $\theta_{\text{prev}} \leftarrow \theta_{\text{cmd}}$; output θ_{cmd} ;

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